

PERCEIVED FACTORS HINDERING THE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF MATHEMATICS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NIGERIA

Abstract:

This paper x-rayed the perceived issues and challenges associated with teaching and learning of mathematics in Nigerian secondary schools. The paper argued that mathematics is a very important subject in secondary schools and highly needed for manpower and technological development of any nation, and as such, needs proper teaching and learning in order to realize the desirable objectives. Some of the challenges facing the teaching and learning of mathematics in Nigeria include unprofessionally trained teachers, inability of the teachers to understand the students, inadequate instructional materials, lack of mathematics laboratories, the inability of the teachers to use different teaching approaches, chock-a-block classes, inability of the mathematics teachers to make full preparation and proper planning. The paper also tried to look into the poor attitude of the students towards mathematics and school location as factors militating against the teaching and learning of mathematics in Nigeria. The paper, however, concluded with recommendations which can be very useful in finding solutions to the challenges, which include, among others, that competently trained mathematics teachers should be recruited and employed to teach mathematics in secondary schools in Nigeria.

Keywords:

Mathematics, Teaching, Learning, Technological development, Performance.

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Introduction

Mathematics is a very desirable tool in all spheres of human endeavour, such as science, engineering, social science and arts. It is the bedrock to which the technological development of any nation is hinged (Oloda, 2021). According to Adetula cited in Oloda (2021), mathematics is the linchpin in the task of national capacity building in science and technology and therefore, any short coming in this subject constitutes drawbacks to the achievement of our science and technology objectives. Mathematics is an indispensable tool for development. The great recognition given to mathematics as a result of its contribution to the development of the society is expected to translate to a satisfactory students' performance in the subject.

The importance of mathematics in the manpower and technological development of any nation cannot be overemphasized. According to Oloda and Fakinlade (2017), mathematics is a discipline that has various areas of study which relate with other disciplines or subjects such as Basic Science, Basic Technology and

others which play important role in the security, sustainability and technological development of any nation. In education, mathematics is the bedrock of all sciences and technologically based subjects. As a core subject, it is offered by all students in secondary schools whether they are science or art inclined and as such it is a “must-pass” subject for any student seeking admission into any field of study either in the universities or other allied tertiary institutions.

The Federal Government of Nigeria (2013) stipulated in her National Policy on Education, the significance of mathematics as one of the core subjects that will enable an individual to gain admission into any higher institution, thereby making it a course that holds the key for further academic progress. To have the chance to study any discipline in the university, polytechnic or college of education, an individual must have obtained a credit pass in mathematics in WASSCE or its equivalent. Unfortunately, several factors have adversely characterize the teaching and learning of this all-important subject at the secondary school level in Nigeria.

Based on the emphasis placed on passing mathematics at the ordinary level in Nigerian educational system, it is essential that mathematics is properly taught so that students can have effective mastery of the subject matter. However, it is unfortunate, that in spite of the importance of mathematics, students’ academic achievement, attitude and interest in mathematics have not improved to a great extent.

The mass failure of students in the recent past in the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria has generated and attracted concerns, criticisms among stakeholders and educators (Awofala & Fatade, 2023; Gbenga-Adeaga, Akinbo & Koiki, 2021; Jega, Muhammad & Gwandu, 2018). According to Awofala & Fatade (2023), WAEC Chief Examiner’s report for mathematics in 2016 showed that students in Nigeria lacked proficiency in basic mathematics areas such as geometry and trigonometry; three-set problem; longitude and latitudes; probability with replacement; coordinates of points and the midpoint of vectors; and the locus of points equidistant from two intersecting lines. This report implies that a large percentage of the students failed to acquire the requisite level of proficiency authorized by the West African Examinations Council and the Ministry of Education in mathematics. While most of the concern is focused on the poor performance, little attention has been given to the contributor(s) of this poor performance. However, some researchers have pointed that one of the possible causes of unsatisfactory performance of secondary school students in mathematics is due largely to poor teaching culture. Improper use of teaching methods and teaching aids create confusion and misconception of mathematics principles in the teaching and learning processes in schools (Tshabalala & Ncube, 2013; Karue & Amukowa, 2013). This was supported by the submission of Jega, Muhammad and Gwandu (2018) that the poor performance of students in Mathematics has to do with the strategies employed by the teacher in attempt to impart knowledge to the learners. The current study addressed the issue of poor performance in mathematics examinations from the perspective of the factors militating against the teaching and learning of the subject among secondary schools in Nigeria.

Factor Militating Against the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics

There are many militating factors that are associated with mathematics teaching and learning in secondary schools in Nigeria.

1. ***Use of Non-competently Trained Teachers:*** A mathematics teacher can be a holder of Nigerian certificate in education (NCE), Bachelor of Science Education (B.Sc. Ed.), Masters of Education (M.Ed.) or Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Mathematics Education, who is employed in educational institution to implement the mathematics curriculum at the level of their professional training acquired (Sunday & Onoge, 2023). Teachers who are not professionally trained in mathematics should not be allowed to teach the subject. In many schools where there are shortage / or no mathematics teachers, teachers of other subjects might be assigned to teach mathematics. This has caused more harm than good in the teaching and learning of mathematics. Such teachers may not be knowledgeable in teaching methods suitable to teach mathematics effectively let alone of being abreast with the use of instructional material to teach mathematics. For a teacher to be able to help students excel in their

mathematics learning process, the teacher must be grounded in mathematics. Mathematics is not a subject that any teacher can teach indiscriminately. Therefore, the teachers who handle mathematics must be authorities, well trained and equipped with necessary skills needed for the job. The submission of Iheanachor (2007) indicated that, there is a significant positive relationship between students' academic achievement in mathematics and teachers' background. A qualified mathematics teacher can easily use different approaches/methods, styles, illustrations, examples, and improvise materials in teaching the students mathematics concepts, principles or ideas which unqualified mathematics teacher cannot do (Anigbo, 2016). A qualified mathematics teacher can arouse students' interest in mathematics learning and ensure success in the learning of the subject through the use of appropriate instructional strategies. Teachers' effectiveness in any particular subject is an important determinant in that subject (Akinoso, 2011). This implies that mathematics teachers who are competent will have their students performing better in mathematics examinations.

- Inability of the Teacher to Understand the Students:*** This deals with the inability of the teacher to handle the different levels of the students' foundation. The constant assessing, grouping and working within the academic skill level of every learner is an uphill task. A teacher needs to understand the children he or she teaches in the classroom. He or she has to understand the differences that exist among his or her children in the class (known as individual differences). Individual differences are another principle of learning which the mathematics teacher should have at the back of his or her mind while planning his or her lessons. Azikwe (1998) observed that no two children are the same physically, mentally and intellectually. Some children are fast learners, while others are slow learners. Some learn faster doing things, others learn faster listening. Some are introverts, and others are extroverts. Some are good at memorization; others are good at discovery. With this view about the children and to accommodate individual differences and variety, the conscientious teacher should therefore select goals, contents, methods and evaluation strategies that will involve every member of the class and serve the purpose of every learner. Recognizing that pupils have diverse learning styles and abilities, teachers should tailor their instruction to meet individual needs. The inability of the teacher to do the stated above, hampers the teaching and learning of mathematics.
- Insufficiency of Instructional Materials:*** Instructional materials are essential tools used for teaching and learning of school subjects to promote teachers' efficiency and improve students' performance. The insufficiency of instructional materials creates a challenge to teaching and learning of mathematics. Huge number of students require a large number of resources. Instructional materials make teaching and learning practical and meaningful. Instructional materials help to concretize the learning process. It offers the learners and their teachers a good opportunity to relate theoretical knowledge to practical experience in the class. Unfortunately, Lawase, Sunday & Ogunode (2021) observed that most educational institutions in Nigeria lack adequate mathematics instructional materials.

In a condition where the needed instructional materials are not accessible, necessary materials should be improvised by the teacher. In line with the above, Stevens in Ghana (2013) contributed that in preparation of the lesson, teacher has to make or improvise the instructional materials needed for his work when the need arises.

- Lack of Mathematics Laboratories:*** Mathematics laboratory is a special room furnished with mathematics resources for the teaching and learning of mathematics (Sunday & Onoge, 2023). Mathematics laboratories are built for the execution of mathematics programme in schools. Appropriate use of mathematics laboratory aids to streamline the teaching and learning of mathematical skills and its availability is crucial for the teaching and learning of mathematics in schools. It is quite unfortunate that many secondary schools across Nigeria do not have mathematics laboratories for their teachers and students; and this has affected the implementation of mathematics curriculum in such schools. Sufficient facilities need to be available in school mathematics laboratories for operative and meaningful teaching and learning of mathematics to take place.

2. **Poor Teaching Methods:** Mathematics as a subject, seems abstract to many students. In order to make it real and draw it very close to the learners, the methods used in teaching it should be of great concern. The teaching and learning of mathematics should be activity-based so that students will be actively involved. Based on this, the subject becomes real to the students. Most of the teachers teaching mathematics are not current with the many methods of teaching the subject. Majority of teachers who have been employed in the past decades have been doing the same thing the same way all along. They have no knowledge of the current ideas and innovations that have taken place in the educational field in the recent past. There are many active learning strategies that can be used in the mathematics classroom. These include, discussion, game playing, project demonstration, discovery, brainstorming, problem solving method and process-based approach. These inculcate in the learners, critical thinking skills, creativity, open mindedness, intellectual honesty, etc. Despite the noble roles of Mathematics in life and modern civilization, it is regrettable that the strategies for teaching and learning of this subject at both primary and secondary levels are still not encouraging (Ejar, Udo & John, 2023)
3. **Chock-a-block Classes:** Teaching mathematics is a very tasking experience. Teachers with larger class sizes will not have proximity to their students which often results in lack of attention. This particularly affects students who are struggling and need extra attention. This will automatically impact learning outcomes negatively, as these students are more likely to have lower test scores and grades as a result. Valerian in Gana (2013) emphasized that not only do large classes affect the quality of teaching delivered, but they can also affect the concentration of the students who are trying to learn in the class. Overcrowding can lead to a disordered classroom environment that will be difficult for the teacher to handle. The large number of students leads to a greater likelihood of disruptive behaviours and skirmishes among students. In some situations, a large number of passive students will sit at the back and relax and do not participate in active learning. Again, when teaching in large classes, teachers provide fewer exercises and practices so as to reduce the workload of marking to avoid illness or stress.

Probably, because of the negative effect of large class size that Caliber Associates in Anigbo (2016), reported that class size of not more than 18 students per teacher is required to produce the greatest benefits. Some professionals may consider a class of fifteen as a large class, whereas some may consider more than thirty as a large class (Gana, 2013). Large classes require a lot of efforts from the teacher to discipline the students. Musa in Sunday & Onoge (2023) submitted that teachers that are teaching large classes are overstretched and are significantly of lower performance. In large mathematics classes, it is best to divide the students into groups.

4. **Lack of Preparation and Planning Among Mathematics Teachers:** Preparation and planning are very important in teaching and learning process. If a teacher is to function well in the class, there is need for him to have adequate preparation and proper planning before he goes into the classroom to teach the students. Stevens in Gana (2013) maintained that a teacher should prepare his lesson meticulously in advance. This is because the entire process of education is being viewed nowadays as a system on interrelated parts. Good planning enables the teachers to state their objectives clearly, select the materials and evaluate the learners in the lesson. Adequate preparation and careful planning enable the teacher to deliver his lesson successfully.
5. **Students' Poor Attitude Towards Mathematics:** Psychologists and educationists hold a strong belief that attitude affects someone's acceptance of a subject and determines achievement in the subject (Farooq & Shah, 2014). In the setting of mathematics, attitude should be viewed as a predisposition to respond in a favourable or unfavourable way to mathematics (Moenikia & Zahed-Babela, 2010). Many students have poor attitude towards mathematics as a subject or field of study. Some students today perceived mathematics as no-go-area because of the negative impressions passed down to them by the past generation who had bad experience with unqualified mathematics teachers which is still in circulation: that mathematics is the most difficult subjects in the school, it is not meant for everybody,

not everybody passes it, it is meant for those with special talent (Audu in Dauda, Jambo & Umar, 2016). Schenkel in Gabina, Jagri, Mohammed, Anass, Abdul-Mumin, Agyei and Domonaamwin (2021) was of the opinion that secondary school students' success in mathematics is dependent on their attitude towards the subject. Most students consider mathematics a difficult subject. Students' perception of any task, especially at the beginning, affects the outcome more than anything else. Students' view and postures towards a subject have the potential to either assist or hinder learning. Moyer-Packenham, Bolyard, Kitsantas, and Oh (2008) maintained that the role attitude plays in limiting the attainment of any success is remarkable. As a result, this suggests that learners should cultivate promising attitude towards mathematics if success is to be achieved.

6. **School Location:** School location is among the factors that can determine the effectiveness of teaching and learning. Secondary schools located in rural and disadvantaged areas, in many occasions, do not have access to quality teachers and required resources to guarantee efficient and effective teaching and learning to take place. It is a common thing to see teachers with better subject knowledge in mathematics deployed to cities and better-resourced schools. According to Sambo (2015) the type of school attended by students can determine their accessibility to learning facilities, calmness learning environment, adequacy of sitting, classroom organisation, as well as interaction among the students. These issues that are related to school location can influence the teaching and learning of mathematics.

Conclusion

Mathematics has been seen as very essential tool in all areas of human endeavour. As one of the compulsory subjects offered in the Nigerian schools, it is designed to develop the mathematical skills of students. The great recognition given to mathematics as a result of its contribution to the development of the society is expected to translate to a satisfactory students' performance in the subject. Mathematics is the fulcrum in the task of national capacity building in science and technology, and therefore, any short coming in this subject constitutes drawbacks to the achievement of our science and technology objectives. Understanding the potentialities of mathematics in contributing to the growth of individuals and the nation at large, students, teachers, persons or group of persons and the governments at all levels, should know that the attainment of educational goals of mathematics in Nigeria must be a principal concern to them. Active teaching in mathematics requires a versatile methodology that involves clear purposes, active learning, real-life applications, and an encouraging classroom atmosphere. The current study has shown that the hindrances to the teaching and learning of mathematics at secondary education level in Nigeria can be attributed to different factors such as the use of unqualified teachers, the inability of the teachers to understand the students, inadequate instructional materials, inappropriate teaching methodology, teachers' poor communication skills, teaching of large classes, inadequate mathematics laboratory, inadequate preparation on the part of the teacher, the attitudes of students towards learning of mathematics and school location.

Recommendations

1. Competently trained mathematics teachers should be recruited and employed to teach mathematics in secondary schools in Nigeria.
2. Mathematics teachers have to be resourceful in terms of methods, approaches, techniques and instructional materials for effective teaching and learning process.
3. Adequate preparation and careful planning are very important in the teaching process. A teacher has to prepare and plan well before going to the class to teach. This will make the teacher to be fully equipped with knowledge, skills, and essential resources, for mathematics teaching and learning.
4. The government should provide well-equipped mathematics laboratories in all the schools alongside other laboratories to safeguard mathematics equipment, concretize the teaching of mathematics, and also projects produced during workshop for further use.

5. More mathematics instructional materials should be provided for mathematics teachers in the country
6. The quality of instruction and effective instructional design according to Dursun and Dede (2004), are necessary to eradicate challenges related to teaching and learning of mathematics.
7. Students should be made to have positive attitudes towards the teaching and learning of mathematics.
8. Mathematics teachers in Nigeria should prioritize the “learner-centred approach” in the Discharge of their duties.

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